

COVID^X

Welcome to the COVID-X vs Healthcare policy series!

[Read more about the policy series](#)

A final event will be held in September in Brussels organized between the COVID-X and the [Inno4cov-19 project](#). Stay tuned to know the exact date and get the final details!

[Clinical Ambassadors](#)

Watch the interview with Humanitas Clinical Ambassadors! Carlotta Cattaneo shares her unique experience of participating in the project.

[Interview](#)

Our collaborations:

We work with a range of parallel projects in common areas of research to maximise our impact and network reach.

Have a look!

COVID-X

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